

Organic acids as a greener alternative for the precipitation of hardwood kraft lignins from the industrial black liquor

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Abstract

The use of three organic acids such as acetic, lactic and citric acid has been investigated as green precipitation agents for kraft lignin isolation from the industrial hardwood black liquor. Chemical composition, molecular structure characteristics in addition to thermal and antioxidant properties were evaluated and compared to kraft lignin precipitated with sulfuric acid. A clear influence of the organic acids was observed in the chemical composition and molecular properties. Organic acids generated lignins with high purity and low ash and carbohydrate contents. FT-IR and Py-GC-MS analyses revealed the ability of organic acids to produce lignins with greater content of methoxylated structures and carbonyl groups than sulfuric acid. Moreover, all evaluated kraft lignins exhibited a suitable radical scavenging activity, and higher than found for commercial antioxidant used as control. TG analysis showed that the employment of organic acids with higher ionic strength lead less thermally stable kraft lignin. In addition, the proximate analysis confirmed the high potential of kraft lignins as an energy source (21-24 MJ/Kg).

Keywords: *Hardwood black liquor, precipitation, organic acids, potential applications*

1. Introduction

Industrial activity generates a vast amount of wastes worldwide. In recent years, the reduction or revalorization of industrial by-products is becoming a relevant social challenge. Further, several of these residues could present very high potential as feedstock in other industries. This is particularly the case of the side-stream generated in the alkaline kraft pulping during the pulp and paper manufacture[1].

Despite the high potential of this abundant waste, paper mills still combust most of the generated black liquor for the production of energy and heat[2,3]. However, at present, there is a considerable bottleneck in several mills, where the recovery boilers have insufficient capacity to process all the generated pulping liquor[4,5]. Thus, the recovery of lignin from the black liquor could be an engaging alternative to combat the excessive generation of this residual flow, as well as to increase the economic profit of the paper mills[6]. Currently, an only small amount (~5%) of kraft lignin is employed for some low-value industrial applications such as additives for concrete admixtures, dust control, feed and food additives, dispersants or binders[7].

Nevertheless, the chemical structure of kraft lignin (softwood and hardwood) with several functional groups makes it a versatile compound for high-value applications in several industrial sectors[1]. Numerous research studies have evidenced the convenient features of this compound as a source for materials[8–10], fuel and chemicals[11–13]. Therefore, the utilization of kraft lignin for new value-added products could promote the exploitation of renewable resources in a more sustainable way, encouraging the circular economy and creating bioindustries based on lignin platform[14].

The extraction of kraft lignin from the black liquor can be carried out by ultrafiltration and precipitation[15], being the last one of the most employed. One-step acidification using sulfuric acid to pH 2-4 results in high lignin recovery yield (90%). However, this method creates problems of great importance during the filtration step and produces high impurity levels on the resultant kraft lignin[16], hindering the industrial use of this compound. Consequently, more recently in 2006, the LignoBoost process has been developed and marketed achieving high purity lignin with low ash content by two-step acidification process[17,18]. In the first one, CO₂ was used to lower the pH to 8-9, while the second stage is carried out at pH between 2 and 4 with sulfuric acid. This strong inorganic acid is widely used all over the world and has huge importance in almost entire industrial segments. Nevertheless, the consumption of sulfuric acid presents various drawbacks such as environmental pollution by the release of harmful gases and the intensification of the acid rain phenomena[19]. In addition to this, since 2012, strong inorganic acids such as sulfuric acid can be classified as carcinogenic to humans.

Therefore, in this research, beyond sulfuric acid, industrial hardwood kraft lignin was obtained by precipitation using organic acids as a cleaner alternative precipitation method. Citric, lactic and acetic acids are some of the most employed organic acids at industrial scale, being citric acid the most used[20]. They are produced by microbial fermentation and chemical synthesis and are considered as no toxic compounds[21].

There are not many research studies, which have looked into the use of organic acids for lignin extraction from the pulping liquor with the objective of promoting the development of more sustainable process by the reduction of the use of sulfuric acid at industrial scale and its replacement with organic acids. Kamble and Bhattacharyulu, 2015[22] precipitated lignin from the kraft black liquor of hardwood and bamboo by using different inorganic acids and acetic acid and the lignin samples were assessed in terms of the chemical structure and thermal stability.

Other authors, focused on the isolation of lignin from hardwood and softwood black liquor with sulfuric acid and three organic acids (formic, citric, and acetic acid) for their evaluation as a source for carbon products[19].

Therefore, the aim of this study was the evaluation of physico-chemical properties of hardwood kraft lignin precipitated using three organic solvents such as acetic, citric and lactic acid and their comparison to the kraft lignin precipitated with sulfuric acid. Several important parameters such as the chemical composition, molecular structure characteristic in addition to thermal and antioxidant properties were analyzed, in order to propose potential applications for this industrial available compound.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Lignin isolation by precipitation with organic acids

Kraft lignins used in this study were isolated by precipitation from an industrial hardwood black liquor from *Eucalyptus sp.* using sulfuric acid and three different organic acids (acetic acid, citric acid and lactic acid). The precipitation with sulfuric acid was performed by adding a desirable amount of concentrated acid to the black liquor under magnetic stirring until reached pH 4 and was allowed to stand for 24 h at room temperature. After that, the precipitated lignin (KL) was filtered and washed until neutral pH. Kraft lignin (KL) was dried at 60 °C for 24 h. In the case of the precipitation using organic acids, the pH as reduced to values of 3.6-5.1, depending on the used organic acid. The recovery step was carried out as in the case of sulfuric acid precipitation method (filtration and washing step). The lignin from acetic acid, lactic acid and citric acid were KLA, KLL and KLC, respectively.

2.2. Chemical composition

The purity of precipitated kraft lignins was evaluated taking into account the carbohydrate content, Klason lignin (AIL) and acid soluble lignin (ASL) content, as well as the ash and sulfur content. For the carbohydrate quantification, lignin samples were subjected to acid hydrolysis with 72% w/w H₂SO₄ for 1 h at 30 °C followed by second acid hydrolysis carried out by diluting the samples to 12% (w/w) H₂SO₄ and autoclaving them for 1 h at 121 °C. After hydrolysis, the samples were filtered and the remaining solid phase was taken as Klason lignin. Hydrolysate liquid was assessed using High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) in a Jasco LC Net II/ADC with an Aminex[®] HPX-87H column (BIO-RAD) (300 x 7.8 mm) equipped with a refractive index detector (RI-2031Plus) and a photodiode array detector (MD-2018Plus). The column operated at 50 °C and the mobile phase (0.005 M H₂SO₄ prepared with 100% deionized and degassed water) pumped at a rate of 0.6 mL/min. the injection volume was 20 µL. Moreover, the hydrolysate was also used to determine ASL with UV-spectrophotometer (band 205 nm). Finally, the ash content was calculated by thermogravimetric analysis in an oxidative atmosphere. To determine the sulfur content, Elemental microanalyzer (TRUSPED MICRO.LECO) was used.

2.3. Gel permeation–high performance liquid chromatography (GPC)

The weight-average (M_w), number-average (M_n) and polydispersity index (IP) of kraft lignins were figured out by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) on a Jasco LC-Net II/ADC device equipped with a RI-2031 Plus Intelligent refractive index detector, PolarGel-M column (300 mm 7.5 mm) and PolarGel-M guard (50 mm 7.5 mm). 0.25 mg of lignin sample was dissolved in 5mL of N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) with 0.1% of lithium bromide and 20 µL of solution were injected. The column operated at 40 °C and eluted with N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) with 0.1% of lithium bromide at a flow of 0.7 mL/min. Polystyrene was used as standard.

2.4. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis

The FT-IR analysis of kraft lignins was carried out on a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FT-IR spectrometer. A total of 64 scans were accumulated in a transmission mode with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. The spectrum was recorded from a range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹.

2.5. Analytical pyrolysis

Precipitated kraft lignin samples were characterized by Py-GC-MS using a 5150 Pyroprobe pyrolyzer (CDS Analytical Inc., Oxford, PA). The identification of the pyrolysis products was performed using a GC-MS instrument (Agilent Techs. Inc. 6890 GC/5973 MSD). The Py-GC-MS was carried out following the method described by Herrera et al., 2014[23]. A quantity between 400-800 mg was pyrolyzed in a quartz boat at 600 °C for 15 s with a heating rate of 20 °C/ms (ramp-off) with the interface kept at 260 °C. The pyrolyzates were purged from the pyrolysis interface into the GC injector under inert conditions using helium gas. The fused-silica capillary column used was an Equity-1701(30 m x 0.20 mm x 0.25 μm). The GC oven program was held at 50 °C and for 2 min. Then it was raised to 120 °C at 10 °C/min (5 min), after that, it was raised to 280 °C at 10 °C/min (8 min) and finally raised to 300 °C at 10 C/min (10 min). The compounds were identified by comparing their mass spectra with the National Institute of Standards Library (NIST) and with compounds reported in the literature[24–28].

2.6. Total phenolic content and antioxidant test

The total phenolic content (TPC) of kraft lignins was determined by the Folin–Ciocalteu spectrophotometric method using gallic acid as a reference compound and dimethyl sulfoxide as a solvent, in a Jasco V-630 spectrophotometer equipment[29]. The DPPH scavenging activity was evaluated using the method described by Brand-Williams et al, 1995[30] with some modifications. DMSO was used to dissolve the lignin samples at different concentrations (0-2 mg/mL). 0.1 mL of lignin solution was added to 3.9 mL DPPH (25mg/L in methanol). The absorbance was measured at 517 nm after 30 min of incubation at room temperature. Commercial antioxidants (Trolox, ascorbic acid and BHT) were used as positive control. Each test was carried out in triplicate.

2.7. Thermogravimetric analyses

Thermal decomposition characteristics of kraft lignins were determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) with Mettler Toledo TGA/SDTA 851 analyzer. 5-10 mg were tested under a nitrogen atmosphere (50 ml/min) at a heating rate of 10 °C/min from 25 °C to 800 °C. Proximate analysis was performed according to the method reported in a previous study[31] and the high heating value (MJ/Kg) was calculated using the equations found in the literature[32,33].

3. Results

3.1. Precipitation yields

Three different organic acids were selected in order to study the replacement of sulfuric acid for the precipitation of lignin from the pulping liquor. The utilization of acetic, citric and lactic acids in the proposed amounts achieved an appropriate reduction of the pH. The pH decreased up to 3.6 with the use of acetic acid getting approximately 133.0 g of lignin/L of black liquor. Similar yield results (133.1 g lignin/L) were observed in the case of lactic acid, where the pH was reduced to 4.2. Lower yield values were obtained using citric acid as precipitating agent (118.4 g lignin/L at pH of 5.1), but similar to using sulfuric acid (120.2 g lignin/L). Regarding the filtration step, several differences were observed between employed acidifying agents. The

recovery of lignin by filtration was difficult and slow in the case of sulfuric and lactic acid, however, the filtration of kraft lignins precipitated with acetic and citric acid resulted quite fast. Other studies also perceived differences during the filtration process with the using of different acidifying agents[34]. Therefore, the replacement of commonly used inorganic acid by organic acids could be an interesting alternative to traditional precipitation method. Moreover, recent studies mentioned that during the precipitation of lignin with organic acids, CO₂ is the main released gas, and thus can be an advantage since it could be used as a precipitating agent as well[19].

3.2. Chemical composition and molecular weight distribution of kraft lignins

The purity of precipitated kraft lignins from hardwood black liquor, which was based on Klason lignin and acid soluble lignin contents, is presented in **Table 1**. Employment of organic acids such as acetic, citric and lactic acids (AA, CA, LA) as acidifying agents produced lignins with higher purity (93-95%) than using sulfuric acid (SA) for the precipitation step (81.8%). Several works have published high purity values (90-94%) for softwood kraft lignins[26,35,36], while the reported purity for hardwood kraft lignins is usually lower[37,38]. Therefore, besides having enhanced the purity of hardwood kraft lignins with the use of organic acids, the reached Klason lignin level is totally comparable to the purity of lignins obtained by Lignoboost process. Conversely, the sulfur content was observed higher in KLA, KLL and KLC than in the kraft lignin precipitated with sulfuric acid and higher than obtained by other authors who used organic acids as precipitating agent[19]. These analyses were repeated several times in order to corroborate the obtained results. No clear reasons were found to explain these results. However, previous works where the chemical reactions during the kraft pulping process together with the usual elemental analyses of the black liquors and the chemistry of the dissolved kraft lignin[39,40] were taken into account to understand and explain these unexpected results. During the kraft pulping, several chemical reactions take place which partially degrade the lignin structure and allow its dissolution in the black liquor[41]. Because of the alkaline conditions of the media the hydroxyl groups of lignin become ionized [42]. Therefore, when some acid is added to the black liquor, the precipitation occurs since the proton concentration [H⁺] increases and hence the protonation of the ionized phenolic groups on the lignin macromolecule happen. The sulfuric acid, as strong acid, is totally dissociated in the alkali media and therefore, phenolic groups were protonated resulting in a lignin with very high hydroxyl groups content (See Table 4). The authors have considered that SO₄⁻ ions from the sulfuric acid could have react with the remained chemicals, which are also in ionic state in the black liquor (Na⁺, HS⁻, OH⁻, CO₃²⁻), forming Na₂SO₄, Na₂S, H₂S or Na₂CO₃. However, in the case of the addition of organic acids as precipitating agent, their lower dissociation capacity in the black liquor, could lead to lower concentration of protons, being not enough to protonate all ionized hydroxyl groups present in the kraft lignin. The hydroxyl groups that were not protonated could have reacted with sulfur derivatives of the media producing -SO₃H groups in lignin[19]. Therefore, the higher sulfur content found in kraft lignin precipitated with organic acids could be originated, not only from the covalently bound sulfur due to the pulping conditions, but also from the precipitation step. Although the amount of sulfur was found higher, the ash content was lower in kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids because of the utilization of organic acids have not formed as many salts as formed during the precipitation with sulfuric acid. Consequently, the precipitation with organic acids has an important positive effect on the ash content but not on the sulfur content. Hence, the use of organic acids for lignin precipitation can be positive progress concerning environmental issues and future commercial potential applications of these industrially available lignins. Regarding the carbohydrate contamination, it is well known that during the kraft cooking process, dissolved lignin fragments

contain covalently bound carbohydrates and as result, they can precipitate with the lignin, being so difficult to eliminate them during the washing step[43]. The results of acid hydrolysis of kraft lignins revealed kraft lignins precipitated with lactic and citric acids had lower carbohydrate contamination than KL. Moreover, common CHO composition was observed for analyzed kraft lignins without notable differences between them. Furthermore, the molecular weight properties of kraft lignins were analyzed in order to know how can affect the use of different organic acids to their final molecular properties. Owing to the strong kraft pulping conditions, which fragmentize the lignin by attacking the ether bonds in order to be removed from the wood, kraft lignins usually present low molecular weight properties[6,44]. Moreover, previous studies reported lower average molecular weight for hardwood kraft lignin than for softwood kraft lignin, because of the higher content of β -aryl ether linkages in hardwood lignin, the smaller amount of C-C bonds between the syringyl units and the lack of reactive positions (C_5 positions) in the aromatic ring for condensation reactions[45]. **Figure 1** shows GPC chromatograms and the corresponding Mn values, Mw values, and polydispersity index (Mw/Mn) are summarized in **Table 1**. As can be observed, the used of acetic acid and lactic acid precipitated very similar lignins in terms of molecular weight distribution. However, kraft lignin precipitated with citric acid had the highest molecular weight distributions as well as the highest polydispersity index. Another author also observed that the employment of citric acid for the kraft lignin precipitation made the lignin high molecular weight and broad molecular weight distribution[34]. Additionally, a clear trend was observed between the molecular weight and the polydispersity of kraft lignins with the strength of the used organic acids. The molecular weight was increased with increased ionic strength (CA>LA>AA) of the organic acid.

3.3. Structural characteristics of kraft lignins

Aside from being very complex the understanding of the molecular structure of lignin compound, several analytical techniques are able to elucidate some of the most important chemical features, such as functional groups and monomeric composition of lignins. The functional groups of kraft lignins were analyzed by FT-IR spectroscopy and the results are displayed in **Figure 2**. All isolated kraft lignins showed typical spectroscopic lignin pattern with small differences in terms of intensity between KL and those precipitated with organic acids. The broad band between 3700 and 3000 cm^{-1} was attributed to aliphatic and aromatic hydroxyl groups stretching vibration[46]. In this region, the most intense absorbance was observed for KL owing to its high hydroxyl groups content (**see Table 4**) and hence, its high moisture content (**Table 6**). Lignins precipitated with organic acids presented sharp and weak peaks at 2971 and 2943 cm^{-1} attributed to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching of C-H in methylene and methyl groups, respectively, whereas in KL these two peaks were more intense. Moreover, only in the spectra of kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids appeared a small signal at 2841 cm^{-1} that corresponds to the C-H stretching of the methoxyl groups. KLA, KLC and KLL showed the presence of carbonyl groups by the stretching vibration of C=O at 1738 cm^{-1} , attributed to ester groups, aldehydes and unconjugated ketones, and at 1700 cm^{-1} , related to the presence of non-conjugated carboxylic acids[47]. On the other hand, in the KL spectra, C=O signal at 1738 cm^{-1} was shown as a shoulder but the signal of carboxylic acids was more intense[1,48]. These results evidenced that kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids manifested higher oxidized substructures in their chemical structure than KL. Signals at 1600 and 1515 cm^{-1} were due to the C=C of the aromatic skeleton vibration and the peaks at 1460 and 1425 cm^{-1} were assigned to C-H deformation in -CH₃ and -CH₂-, respectively. The signal at 1365 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the aliphatic C-H stretch in -CH₃ of syringyl unit, was only observed in the case of kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids. Moreover, the peak at 1330 cm^{-1} demonstrated the presence of syringyl units

(aromatic ring breathing), while no signals of guaiacyl units were found in any kraft lignin sample. Some characteristic bands associated with elemental units in lignin molecule were detected at 1220, 1110 and 1025 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C-C, C-O and C=O stretching, aromatic C-H in-plane deformation (S) and aromatic C-H in-plane deformation (G). Moreover, syringyl/guaiacyl ratio (S/G) of different kraft lignins was figured out using analytical pyrolysis (Py-GC-MS) at 600 °C. Released products during pyrolysis are usually related to phenols, acids, esters, and aldehydes. **Table 2** collects the identification of 29 phenolic compounds, which represents 93-96 % of the lignin samples. The identified pyrolysis products were classified into four categories according to their aromatic structure: phenol-type compounds (H), guaiacyl-type compounds (G), syringol-type compounds (S), and catechol-type compounds (Ca). Although in all kraft lignin samples the majority of compounds liberated during the pyrolysis derived from syringyl units, as expected for coming from hardwood, as regards to the monomeric composition, significant differences were observed between them. Despite the origin being the main responsible of the monomeric composition of the lignin molecule, this work evidenced that the precipitation step also has a significant contribution to the final chemical structure. Lignins precipitated with organic acids presented higher S/G ratio than kraft lignin precipitated with sulfuric acid, especially in the case of lignins precipitated with citric and lactic acids; where around 76 % of syringyl units and 14-16% of guaiacyl units were found. Therefore, the use of organic acids for the precipitation of lignin, apparently, promote the generation of lignins with less condensed structures because of their higher content on S-unit. The content of S unit is widely related to the degree of condensation in lignins since the presence of methoxyl groups in C₃ and C₅ positions of the aromatic ring avoid the formation of the condensed bonds like β -5' and, especially 5-5', which is formed during the pulping stage[49]. In addition, a high amount of fatty acids derivatives (esters) were detected in the case of kraft lignin precipitated with sulfuric acid. The presence of fatty acids is commonly associated with the origin and their resistance to thermochemical extraction processes[50,51]. However, in the case of lignins precipitated with organic acids, substantially lower amount of fatty acid derivatives was observed (< 2%), confirming once again, that the use of organic acids for the recovery of kraft lignin from the industrial black liquor makes the resultant lignin less contaminated of impurities. Additionally, in order to get a better understanding about the structure differences between precipitated kraft lignins, lignin-originated pyrolysis products were grouped according to their structural characteristics, as was reported in previous work[14] (**Table 3**). This analysis provided useful information and showed clear structural differences between isolated kraft lignins. The results demonstrated that kraft lignins from the precipitation using organic acids presented higher content of methoxylated phenolic substructures than KL, and these substructures were more abundant as increasing the ionic strength of the organic acid used for the precipitation. On the other hand, it was observed that guaiacyl and syringyl derived compounds with non-substituted saturated chains were less abundant in the case of the kraft lignins isolated with organic acids than in KL. In general, KLA, KLL and KLC showed higher content of units with unsaturated side chains and oxygen-containing groups in the side chains than KL. The highest amount for these two functional groups was found for KLA, and it was noticed a clear reduction as the ionic strength of the organic acid increased. Although double C=C bonds can be formed during the pyrolysis process[14], oxidized substructures come from the original chemical structure when lignin is pyrolyzed[52]. Therefore, the use of organic acids generated lignins with the largest amount of aromatic substructures containing aldehydes and ketones, which indicated the presence of greater content of carbonyl groups in the chemical structure. This result is in accordance with the FTIR, which showed that characteristic absorption of C=O stretching vibration was stronger in the case of KLA, KLL and KLC.

3.4. TPC and antioxidant activity

Table 4 shows the results of Folin-Ciocalteu and DPPH test of isolated kraft lignins. KL presented higher total phenolic content than kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids. Moreover, it was observed that the organic acids used to isolate lignins from the black liquor influenced the phenolic content, being lower when stronger organic acid was used. In addition, the inhibitory effect of kraft lignin samples, which was expressed as “Efficient Concentration value (IC₅₀)”, was higher than found for commercial antioxidant BHT but lower than exhibited for ascorbic acid and Trolox. Although KLA presented the highest antioxidant activity, no significant differences were detected between evaluated kraft lignin samples. Probably, the highest antioxidant behavior of KLA was due to its chemical structure which is the main responsible of this property. Aside from phenolic groups, there are other functional groups in the chemical structure, which greatly affect to the antioxidant capacity of lignins. Substituents like methoxyl groups and conjugated double bonds can stabilize phenoxyl radicals by resonance providing a positive effect on the antioxidant behavior of lignins[53,54]. In addition, having low molecular weight and narrow polydispersity is also beneficial for antioxidant properties[55]. KLA presented high content of methoxyl groups as well as conjugated double bonds in its structure. Moreover, it had the lowest molecular weight and polydispersity of all evaluated samples. Furthermore, impurities such as a carbohydrate or ash content have a negative effect on antioxidant activity[56] and KLA presented the lowest ash content and low carbohydrate content in its chemical composition.

3.5. Thermal degradation and proximate analysis

Thermogravimetric analysis is an appropriate technique to analyse the thermal stability of lignin compound as well as to carry out the proximate analysis assay. Thermal degradation behavior of lignin is an indispensable data to focus the industrial use of kraft lignin on a specific application[57]. The thermogravimetric (TG) and first derivative (DTG) curves of kraft lignins under nitrogen atmosphere are presented in **Figure 3** and the main characteristic temperatures together with the char residue are summarized in **Table 5**. Isolated kraft lignins showed different degradation profiles, evidencing variations in their chemical structure (functional groups, monomeric composition, and molecular weight)[58], which was clearly influenced by the precipitation method (acidifying agent). With regards to the thermal stability of kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids, it was detected that the use of stronger acid leads to less thermally stable lignin. However, KLA presented slightly higher thermal decomposition temperatures than KL. It was previously reported that lignins with high ether bonds content and low condensation degrees in their chemical structure usually have lower thermal stability[59,60]. It is widely associated with the S unit content in the monomeric composition of lignin. Normally, high methoxyl content or high S/G ratio limit the formation of C-C linkages. Moreover, the lower total phenolic content for kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids indicated that they could present more ether bonds in their structure. Several weight loss stages were observed in the DTG curves. The first weight loss stage (3-7%) below 100 °C was attributed to the gradual evaporation of moisture. The highest moisture content of KL can be related to the presence of the greater amount of hydrophilic groups in its structure like hydroxyl groups content. In addition, lignin samples exhibited a small degradation step at around 150°C, probably due to the presence of fatty acids detected in the Py-GC-MS. Regarding the decomposition of lignin, two main degradation steps were observed. The first one was centered between 230-245 °C. This first weight loss stage was related to dehydration of the hydroxyl group located in the benzyl group and the fragmentation of β -aryl and α -aryl ether inter-units linkage[61]. The maximum degradation rate (T_{max2}) was

identified between 327-365 °C. During this degradation step, aliphatic side chains start splitting off from the aromatic ring (~300 °C). After that, methyl-aryl ether bond and carbon-carbon cleavage (300-400 °C) between structural units take place[57]. In addition, proximate analysis was carried out in order to evaluate the potential of isolated kraft lignins as a solid fuel additive or feedstock for carbon-based materials. The results of moisture, ash content, volatile matter and fixed carbon in addition to HHV (MJ/Kg) are described in **Table 6**. Although lignin, like other biomass materials, is composed of moisture, ash and organic matter (volatiles and fixed carbon), the content of these components varies significantly compared to lignocellulosic materials commonly used for the production of heat or electricity[32]. The moisture content and volatile matter of kraft lignins were lower than those found in the literature for commercial solid fuels, while the fixed carbon content was significantly higher. Moreover, heating values of kraft lignin (20-22 MJ/Kg), were higher than reported for wood, annual plants and agricultural residues[33,62]. Another important parameter to consider during thermal conversion is the ash content, which has a very negative effect generating harmful emissions and slag deposits that creating thermal resistance to heat transfer[31]. In this study, a great reduction of ash content was observed by the use of organic acids as precipitating agents. The HHV was slightly higher in the case of lignins isolated with organic acids. The low ash content together with the suitable heating value, confirm the high potential of kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids as an energy source. Moreover, the high fixed carbon content makes lignin a good precursor for carbon-based products.

3.6. Potential application perspectives of kraft lignins

The generation of such an abundant industrial side-product as black liquor, cannot be ignored and requires strategies for its revalorization. Integrating the biorefinery in the current technologies, such as kraft mills, would exploit in a more efficient way the renewable sources creating new products and markets. Kraft lignin presents great potential to be used as feedstock for several industrial fields. For instance, the high fixed carbon content and char yields values of kraft lignins make them suitable for the elaboration of carbon-based materials (activated carbon or carbon fibers). Particularly, for the manufacture of carbon fibers, where properties like high purity level, low Mw and less branched structure are necessary[43,63]. In this work, the utilization of organic acids for the precipitation step produced high pure lignins, with reduced ash and carbohydrate contents. Although kraft lignins usually contain high-condensed structures because of the pulping process, in this case, their structure was mainly based on syringyl units because of their origin (hardwood). In addition, the highest syringyl content was observed for kraft lignins obtained by the use of organic acids, suggesting their low content of condensed structures. Further, to use lignin as a precursor of carbon products, low thermal degradation temperatures are required[22]. Conversely, the thermal stability (onset temperature) of lignins is a critical parameter that can limit their application in polymeric field[31]. This study reported decomposition temperatures above 200 °C for isolated kraft lignins, making them able to be incorporated as an additive in polymeric matrices, which are processed at lower temperatures. Moreover, the chemical structure of kraft lignins with several functional groups like hydroxyl or carbonyl groups, makes them suitable for chemical transformations, suggesting a bright future for lignin-based polymeric materials[9]. Furthermore, kraft lignins as polyphenolic compound could act as potential antioxidant for food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries instead of BHT. BHT is a regulated commercial antioxidants widely used in EU in several fields, but, recently, there are huge concerns about the side effects of this synthetic compound after a long time use[64–66]. Nevertheless, the lignin as cosmetic or pharmaceutical product, is still not regulated by the EU Commission since deeper studies about safety of lignin compound in humans are completely

necessary. An additional engaging application could be the use of kraft lignins as bio-additive for solid fuels. Though different solid fuels can be used for energy production, wood pellets have experienced a large increase during the last decade. Recently, the manufacture of pellets with high quality and high fuel-value by the incorporation functional bio-additives is receiving large attention[67,68]. In this context, isolated kraft lignins could play an important role because of their high purity, low ash content and high heating value. Other works have demonstrated that, besides producing sustainable and environmentally friendly pellets from nontoxic and cheap raw materials by the addition of kraft lignin, manufactured pellets had improved mechanical durability as well as a higher heating value[68,69].

Conclusions

This work provides a novel information about the influence of using a cleaner and greener way to obtain kraft lignin from hardwood industrial black liquor. Aside from presenting analysis of their chemical composition and their main structural characteristics, antioxidants and thermal studies were also carried out in order to promote applications for this unexploited industrial waste. The use of organic acids as precipitating agents, generated kraft lignins with higher purity than with the employment of traditional sulfuric acid. Moreover, this study reports the influence of evaluated organic acids on the chemical structure of kraft lignins. A clear relation was observed between the ionic strength of the organic acids with the molecular features (functional groups, monomeric composition, and molecular weight) of kraft lignins. Pyrolysis analysis demonstrated that kraft lignins precipitated with organic acids presented higher content of methoxylated phenolic substructures than KL as well as higher amount of functional groups such as carbonyl groups and carbon-carbon double bonds. These structural features together with their chemical composition, rich in phenolic compounds, contribute to their potent antioxidant activity, which was found higher than commonly used commercial synthetic antioxidant (BHT). Furthermore, thermal analysis revealed that the use of stronger organic acid lead to less thermally stable lignin, but in all cases, decomposition temperatures were detected above 200 °C. In addition, the proximate analysis confirmed the high potential of kraft lignins as an energy source (21-24 MJ/Kg).

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Referencias

- [1] R. Martín-Sampedro, J.I. Santos, Ú. Fillat, B. Wicklein, M.E. Eugenio, D. Ibarra, Characterization of lignins from *Populus alba* L. generated as by-products in different transformation processes: Kraft pulping, organosolv and acid hydrolysis, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 126 (2019) 18–29. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.12.158.
- [2] T. V. Lourençon, F.A. Hansel, T.A. Da Silva, L.P. Ramos, G.I.B. De Muniz, W.L.E. Magalhães, Hardwood and softwood kraft lignins fractionation by simple sequential acid precipitation, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 154 (2015) 82–88. doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2015.09.015.
- [3] A. Van Heiningen, Converting a kraft pulp mill into an integrated forest biorefinery, *Pulp Pap. Canada.* 107 (2006) 38–43.
- [4] E. Välimäki, P. Niemi, K. Haaga, A case study on the effects of lignin recovery on recovery boiler

- operation, in: 2010 Int. Chem. Recover. Conf., 2010: pp. 148–159. <http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=2-s2.0-77956771543&partnerID=40&md5=dd1d374b61fe70efc4c6af22028c8825>.
- [5] A.S. Jönsson, A.K. Nordin, O. Wallberg, Concentration and purification of lignin in hardwood kraft pulping liquor by ultrafiltration and nanofiltration, *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 86 (2008) 1271–1280. doi:10.1016/j.cherd.2008.06.003.
- [6] T.Q. Yuan, J. He, F. Xu, R.C. Sun, Fractionation and physico-chemical analysis of degraded lignins from the black liquor of Eucalyptus pellita KP-AQ pulping, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 94 (2009) 1142–1150. doi:10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2009.03.019.
- [7] V. Passoni, C. Scarica, M. Levi, S. Turri, G. Griffini, Fractionation of Industrial Softwood Kraft Lignin: Solvent Selection as a Tool for Tailored Material Properties, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 4 (2016) 2232–2242. doi:10.1021/acssuschemeng.5b01722.
- [8] D. Kun, B. Pukánszky, Polymer/lignin blends: Interactions, properties, applications, *Eur. Polym. J.* 93 (2017) 618–641. doi:10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2017.04.035.
- [9] S. Laurichesse, L. Avérous, Chemical modification of lignins: Towards biobased polymers, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 39 (2014) 1266–1290. doi:10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2013.11.004.
- [10] A. Naseem, S. Tabasum, K.M. Zia, M. Zuber, M. Ali, A. Noreen, Lignin-derivatives based polymers, blends and composites: A review, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 93 (2016) 296–313. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2016.08.030.
- [11] A. Berlin, M. Balakshin, *Industrial Lignins: Analysis, Properties, and Applications*, Elsevier, 2014. doi:10.1016/B978-0-444-59561-4.00018-8.
- [12] M.P. Pandey, C.S. Kim, Lignin Depolymerization and Conversion: A Review of Thermochemical Methods, *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 34 (2011) 29–41. doi:10.1002/ceat.201000270.
- [13] L. Hodásová, M. Jablonsky, A. Skulcova, A. Haz, Lignin , potential products and their market value, *Wood Res.* 60 (2015) 973–986.
- [14] J. Ponomarenko, T. Dizhbite, M. Lauberts, A. Viksna, G. Dobele, O. Bikovens, G. Telysheva, Characterization of softwood and hardwood lignoboost kraft lignins with emphasis on their antioxidant activity, *BioResources.* 9 (2014) 2051–2068. doi:10.15376/biores.9.2.2051-2068.
- [15] M.A. Gilarranz, F. Rodríguez, M. Oliet, J.A. Revenga, Acid precipitation and purification of wheat straw lignin, *Sep. Sci. Technol.* 33 (1998) 1359–1377. doi:10.1080/01496399808544988.
- [16] F. Öhman, H. Wallmo, H. Theliander, A novel method for washing lignin precipitated from kraft black liquor – Laboratory trials, *Nord. Pulp Pap. Res. J.* 22 (2007) 9–16. doi:10.3183/npprj-2007-22-01-p009-016.
- [17] W. Zhu, H. Theliander, Precipitation of lignin from softwood black liquor: An investigation of the equilibrium and molecular properties of lignin, *BioResources.* 10 (2015) 1696–1714. doi:10.15376/biores.10.1.1696-1715.
- [18] W. Zhu, G. Westman, H. Theliander, Investigation and characterization of lignin precipitation in the lignoboost process, *J. Wood Chem. Technol.* 34 (2014) 77–97. doi:10.1080/02773813.2013.838267.
- [19] M. Namane, F. José García-Mateos, B. Sithole, D. Ramjugernath, J. Rodríguez-Mirasol, T. Cordero, Characteristics of Lignin Precipitated With Organic Acids As a Source for Valorisation of Carbon Products, *Cellul. Chem. Technol.* 50 (2016) 3–4.
- [20] P. Singh Nee Nigam, Production of organic acids from agro-industrial residues, in: *Biotechnol. Agro-Industrial Residues Util. Util. Agro-Residues*, 2009: pp. 37–60. doi:10.1007/978-1-4020-9942-7_3.
- [21] L.P.S. Vandenberghe, S.G. Karp, P.Z. de Oliveira, J.C. de Carvalho, C. Rodrigues, C.R. Soccol, Solid-State Fermentation for the Production of Organic Acids, in: *Curr. Dev. Biotechnol. Bioeng.*, 2017: pp. 415–434. doi:10.1016/b978-0-444-63990-5.00018-9.

- [22] S. V Kamble, Y.C. Bhattacharyulu, Selective separation of biomass from black liquor waste by inorganic and organic acids, *Int. J. Adv. Res. Journal* www.journalijar.com *Int. J. Adv. Res.* 3 (2015) 684–692.
- [23] R. Herrera, X. Erdocia, R. Llano-Ponte, J. Labidi, Characterization of hydrothermally treated wood in relation to changes on its chemical composition and physical properties, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis.* 107 (2014) 256–266. doi:10.1016/j.jaap.2014.03.010.
- [24] L. Chen, X. Wang, H. Yang, Q. Lu, D. Li, Q. Yang, H. Chen, Study on pyrolysis behaviors of non-woody lignins with TG-FTIR and Py-GC/MS, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis.* 113 (2015) 499–507. doi:10.1016/J.JAAP.2015.03.018.
- [25] J. Fernández-Rodríguez, O. Gordobil, E. Robles, M. González-Alriols, J. Labidi, Lignin valorization from side-streams produced during agricultural waste pulping and total chlorine free bleaching, *J. Clean. Prod.* 142 (2017). doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.10.198.
- [26] H. Li, A.G. McDonald, Fractionation and characterization of industrial lignins, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 62 (2014) 67–76. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2014.08.013.
- [27] D. Schorr, P.N. Diouf, T. Stevanovic, Evaluation of industrial lignins for biocomposites production, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 52 (2014) 65–73. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2013.10.014.
- [28] C.H. Vane, The molecular composition of lignin in spruce decayed by white-rot fungi (*Phanerochaete chrysosporium* and *Trametes versicolor*) using pyrolysis-GC-MS and thermochemolysis with tetramethylammonium hydroxide, *Int. Biodeterior. Biodegrad.* 51 (2003) 67–75. doi:10.1016/S0964-8305(02)00089-6.
- [29] O. Gordobil, R. Herrera, M. Yahyaoui, S. Ilk, M. Kaya, J. Labidi, Potential use of kraft and organosolv lignins as a natural additive for healthcare products, *RSC Adv.* 8 (2018) 24525–24533. doi:10.1039/c8ra02255k.
- [30] W. Brand-Williams, M.E. Cuvelier, C. Berset, Use of a free radical method to evaluate antioxidant activity, *LWT - Food Sci. Technol.* 28 (1995) 25–30. doi:10.1016/S0023-6438(95)80008-5.
- [31] O. Gordobil, R. Moriana, L. Zhang, J. Labidi, O. Sevastyanova, Assessment of technical lignins for uses in biofuels and biomaterials: Structure-related properties, proximate analysis and chemical modification, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 83 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2015.12.048.
- [32] R. García, C. Pizarro, A.G. Lavín, J.L. Bueno, Spanish biofuels heating value estimation. Part II: Proximate analysis data, *Fuel.* 117 (2014) 1139–1147. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2013.08.049.
- [33] T. Cordero, F. Marquez, J. Rodriguez-Mirasol, J. Rodriguez, Predicting heating values of lignocellulosics and carbonaceous materials from proximate analysis, *Fuel.* 80 (2001) 1567–1571. doi:10.1016/S0016-2361(01)00034-5.
- [34] Z. Liu, X.G. Luo, Y. Li, L. Li, Y. Huang, Extraction of Lignin from Pulping Black Liquor by Organic Acid, *Mater. Sci. Forum.* 620–622 (2009) 571–574. doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/msf.620-622.571.
- [35] C.G. Boeriu, D. Bravo, R.J.A. Gosselink, J.E.G. Van Dam, Characterisation of structure-dependent functional properties of lignin with infrared spectroscopy, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 20 (2004) 205–218. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2004.04.022.
- [36] J. Domínguez-Robles, T. Tamminen, T. Liitiä, M.S. Peresin, A. Rodríguez, A.S. Jääskeläinen, Aqueous acetone fractionation of kraft, organosolv and soda lignins, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 106 (2018) 979–987. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2017.08.102.
- [37] O. Gordobil, R. Delucis, I. Egüés, J. Labidi, Kraft lignin as filler in PLA to improve ductility and thermal properties, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 72 (2015). doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2015.01.055.
- [38] O. Gordobil, R. Moriana, L. Zhang, J. Labidi, O. Sevastyanova, Assessment of technical lignins for uses in biofuels and biomaterials: Structure-related properties, proximate analysis and chemical modification, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 83 (2016) 155–165. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2015.12.048.
- [39] W. Zhu, H. Theliander, Equilibrium of lignin precipitation, *Proc. 16th ISWFPC.* (2011). http://publications.lib.chalmers.se/records/fulltext/local_155700.pdf.

- [40] B.T.T. Dang, H. Theliander, H. Brelid, T. Köhnke, Effect of sodium ion concentration profile during softwood kraft pulping on delignification rate, xylan retention and reactions of hexenuronic acids, *Nord. Pulp Pap. Res. J.* 29 (2014) 604–611. doi:10.3183/npprj-2014-29-04-p604-611.
- [41] F.S. Chakar, A.J. Ragauskas, Review of current and future softwood kraft lignin process chemistry, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 20 (2004) 131–141. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2004.04.016.
- [42] W. Zhu, H. Theliander, Lignin precipitation, *BioResources.* 10 (2015) 1696–1714. https://bioresources.cnr.ncsu.edu/BioRes_10/BioRes_10_1_1696_Zhu_T_Precipitation_Lignin_Softwood_Black_Liquor_6518.pdf.
- [43] A.P. Dodd, J.F. Kadla, S.K. Straus, Characterization of fractions obtained from two industrial softwood kraft lignins, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 3 (2015) 103–110. doi:10.1021/sc500601b.
- [44] H. Chung, N.R. Washburn, Chemistry of lignin-based materials, *Green Mater.* 1 (2012) 137–160. doi:10.1680/gmat.12.00009.
- [45] W. Zhu, Equilibrium of Lignin Precipitation The Effects of pH, Temperature, Ion Strength and Wood Origins Equilibrium of Lignin Precipitation, 2013. <http://publications.lib.chalmers.se/records/fulltext/186940/186940.pdf>.
- [46] O. Gordobil, I. Egüés, R. Llano-Ponte, J. Labidi, Physicochemical properties of PLA lignin blends, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 108 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2014.01.002.
- [47] N. Cachet, S. Camy, B. Benjelloun-Mlayah, J.S. Condoret, M. Delmas, Esterification of organosolv lignin under supercritical conditions, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 58 (2014) 287–297. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2014.03.039.
- [48] A. Toledano, L. Serrano, A. Garcia, I. Mondragon, J. Labidi, Comparative study of lignin fractionation by ultrafiltration and selective precipitation, *Chem. Eng. J.* 157 (2010) 93–99. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2009.10.056.
- [49] K.M. Holtman, H.M. Chang, H. Jameel, J.F. Kadla, Quantitative ¹³C NMR characterization of milled wood lignins isolated by different milling techniques, *J. Wood Chem. Technol.* 26 (2006) 21–34. doi:10.1080/02773810600582152.
- [50] S. Constant, H.L.J. Wienk, A.E. Frissen, P. de Peinder, R. Boelens, D.S. van Es, R.J.H. Grisel, B.M. Weckhuysen, W.J.J. Huijgen, R.J.A. Gosselink, P.C.A. Bruijninx, New insights into the structure and composition of technical lignins: a comparative characterisation study, *Green Chem.* 18 (2016) 2651–2665. doi:10.1039/C5GC03043A.
- [51] W.J.J. Huijgen, J.H. Reith, H. den Uil, Pretreatment and Fractionation of Wheat Straw by an Acetone-Based Organosolv Process, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 49 (2010) 10132–10140. doi:10.1021/ie101247w.
- [52] X. Lin, S. Sui, S. Tan, C. Pittman, J. Sun, Z. Zhang, Fast Pyrolysis of Four Lignins from Different Isolation Processes Using Py-GC/MS, *Energies.* 8 (2015) 5107–5121. doi:10.3390/en8065107.
- [53] X. Pan, J.F. Kadla, K. Ehara, N. Gilkes, J.N. Saddler, Organosolv ethanol lignin from hybrid poplar as a radical scavenger: Relationship between lignin structure, extraction conditions, and antioxidant activity, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 54 (2006) 5806–5813. doi:10.1021/jf0605392.
- [54] T. Dizhbite, G. Telysheva, V. Jurkjane, U. Viesturs, Characterization of the radical scavenging activity of lignins - Natural antioxidants, *Bioresour. Technol.* 95 (2004) 309–317. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2004.02.024.
- [55] M.P. Vinardell, V. Ugartondo, M. Mitjans, Potential applications of antioxidant lignins from different sources, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 27 (2008) 220–223. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2007.07.011.
- [56] M.F. Li, S.N. Sun, F. Xu, R.C. Sun, Mild acetosolv process to fractionate bamboo for the biorefinery: Structural and antioxidant properties of the dissolved lignin, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 60 (2012) 1703–1712. doi:10.1021/jf2050608.
- [57] S.Y. Park, J.Y. Kim, H.J. Youn, J.W. Choi, Fractionation of lignin macromolecules by sequential organic solvents systems and their characterization for further valuable applications, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 106 (2018) 793–802. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2017.08.069.

- [58] O. Sevastyanova, G. Dobele, V. Jurkjane, A. Svärd, E. Brännvall, Effect of raw material and pulping conditions on the properties of dissolved kraft lignin, in: 13th Eur. Work. Lignocellul. Pulp, EWLP 2014, June 24-27, 2014, Seville, Spain. Proc., 2014: pp. 9–12. <http://www.irnas.csic.es/users/delrio/Proceedings-13thEWLP.pdf>.
- [59] H. Li, A.G. McDonald, Fractionation and characterization of industrial lignins, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 62 (2014) 67–76. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2014.08.013.
- [60] F. Monteil-Rivera, M. Phuong, M. Ye, A. Halasz, J. Hawari, Isolation and characterization of herbaceous lignins for applications in biomaterials, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 41 (2013) 356–364. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2012.04.049.
- [61] F. Bertini, M. Canetti, A. Cacciamani, G. Elegir, M. Orlandi, L. Zoia, Effect of ligno-derivatives on thermal properties and degradation behavior of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate)-based biocomposites, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 97 (2012) 1979–1987. doi:10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2012.03.009.
- [62] J.F. Saldarriaga, R. Aguado, A. Pablos, M. Amutio, M. Olazar, J. Bilbao, Fast characterization of biomass fuels by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), *Fuel.* 140 (2015) 744–751. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2014.10.024.
- [63] I. Norberg, Carbon fibres from kraft lignin, Chemical Science and Engineering, Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), 2012.
- [64] J.L. Espinoza-Acosta, P.I. Torres-Chávez, B. Ramírez-Wong, C.M. López-Saiz, B. Montañón-Leyva, Antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antimutagenic properties of technical lignins and their applications, *BioResources.* 11 (2016) 5452–5481. doi:10.15376/biores.11.2.Espinoza_Acosta.
- [65] A.K. Bauer, L.D. Dwyer-Nield, J.A. Hankin, R.C. Murphy, A.M. Malkinson, The lung tumor promoter, butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), causes chronic inflammation in promotion-sensitive BALB/cByJ mice but not in promotion-resistant C57BL/6 mice., *Toxicology.* 169 (2001) 1–15. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11696405> (accessed April 30, 2019).
- [66] C.P. Jayalakshmi, J.D. Sharma, Effect of butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) and butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) on rat erythrocytes., *Environ. Res.* 41 (1986) 235–8. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/3757972> (accessed December 20, 2017).
- [67] J. Stevens, D.J. Gardner, Enhancing the fuel value of wood pellets with the addition of lignin., *Wood Fiber Sci.* 42 (2010) 439–443.
- [68] A. Abedi, A.K. Dalai, Study on the quality of oat hull fuel pellets using bio-additives, *Biomass and Bioenergy.* 106 (2017) 166–175. doi:10.1016/j.biombioe.2017.08.024.
- [69] J. Berghel, S. Frodeson, K. Granström, R. Renström, M. Ståhl, D. Nordgren, P. Tomani, The effects of kraft lignin additives on wood fuel pellet quality, energy use and shelf life, *Fuel Process. Technol.* 112 (2013) 64–69. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2013.02.011.

Figure Captions

Figure 1. GPC chromatograms of isolated Kraft lignins.

Figure 2. FTIR spectra of precipitated Kraft lignin with sulfuric acid and different organic acids.

Figure 3. TG and DTG curves of lignin samples.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Tables

Table 1. Chemical composition of lignins and molecular weight distributions.

	KL	KLA	KLL	KLC
Klason lignin (%)	75.4 ± 2.66	89.9 ± 0.91	88.7 ± 2.90	89.6 ± 1.21
Acid soluble lignin (%)	6.4 ± 0.25	4.2 ± 0.19	5.6 ± 0.46	3.9 ± 0.49
Carbohydrate content (%)	0.60 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.09	0.33 ± 0.09	0.13 ± 0.02
Ash content (%) ^a	4.68	0.07	1.02	1.99
C (%)	56.67	57.53	55.41	55.45
H (%)	4.88	4.89	4.99	5.04
N (%) ^b	0.65	0.44	0.44	0.49
O (%) ^c	32.32	30.62	32.02	32.05
S (%)	5.49	6.53	6.39	6.98
Mn	510	458	458	806
Mw	2416	1824	2005	4187
IP	4.7	3.9	4.4	5.2

^a Determined by TGA; ^b nd: Results out of reach (<1.6%); ^c Calculated by difference.

Table 2. Identification of the pyrolysis products from four lignin samples their mass fragments.

Compound	Area percentage (%)				Mass fragments
	KL	KLA	KLL	KLC	
Phenol	0.30	0.31	0.25	0.19	94/66/65
p-cresol	0.44	0.42	0.31	0.22	107/108/77
o-cresol	0.47	0.26	0.19	nd	108/107/79
4-Ethylphenol	0.58	nd	nd	0.17	107/122/77
m-xylenol	nd	nd	0.18	nd	122/107/121
<i>Total</i>	<i>1.79</i>	<i>0.99</i>	<i>0.94</i>	<i>0.58</i>	
Catechol	1.71	nd	0.76	1.02	110/64/63
3-Methoxycatechol	11.19	11.67	9.42	7.75	140/125/97
4-Methylcatechol	0.60	0.88	0.56	0.38	124/123/78
Pyrocatechol	0.81	nd	nd	nd	110/82
<i>Total</i>	<i>14.32</i>	<i>12.55</i>	<i>10.74</i>	<i>9.15</i>	
Guaiacol	5.01	3.69	5.63	8.35	109/124/81
3-Methylguaiacol	1.12	nd	nd	0.58	123/138/77
4-Methylguaiacol	6.04	6.57	2.99	1.47	138/123/95
4-Vinylguaiacol	2.62	1.94	2.04	2.32	150/135/107
4-Ethylguaiacol	4.04	2.17	1.78	0.91	137/152/122
Isoeugenol	1.04	0.59	0.43	0.33	164/77/149
Vanillin	0.72	1.24	0.92	1.15	151/152/81
Guaiacyl acetone	0.32	0.64	0.47	0.47	137/180/122
Acetoguaiacone	0.42	0.62	0.61	0.42	151/123/166
4-Propylguaiacol	0.38	0.55	Nd	nd	137/166/122
<i>Total</i>	<i>21.70</i>	<i>18.01</i>	<i>14.87</i>	<i>15.99</i>	
Syringol	17.78	17.78	30.47	44.65	154/139/111
4-Methylsyringol	13.42	15.08	13.74	6.86	168/153/125
4-Ethylsyringol	5.56	5.89	5.31	3.12	167/182/168
4-Vynilsyringol	5.03	5.59	5.23	5.43	180/165/137
4-Allylsyringol	4.91	8.47	6.62	5.35	194/91/179
3,4-dimethoxyphenol	nd	0.60	1.83	nd	154/139/151
Acetosyringone	nd	0.67	0.72	0.77	181/196/153
Syringaldehyde	nd	1.72	1.10	0.97	182/181/111
4-Propylsyringol	0.97	1.13	0.89	0.39	167/196/168
<i>Total</i>	<i>47.67</i>	<i>56.92</i>	<i>65.91</i>	<i>67.54</i>	
Furan derivatives	0.30	0.06	0.10	nd	
Fatty acids	4.78	1.99	0.86	0.64	
S/G	2.86	3.86	5.16	4.80	

Table 3. Relative content (%) of groups of lignin-derived compound with phenolic hydroxyl groups and other specific functional groups.

Pyrolysis products	KL	KLA	KLL	KLC
Methoxylated phenolic groups (%) ^a	80.56	86.60	90.19	91.28
Non-substituted saturated chains (%) ^b	33.62	32.95	25.95	14.11
Unsaturated side chains (C=C) (%)	13.59	16.59	14.33	13.43
Oxygenated groups in the side chains (C=O) (%)	1.46	4.88	3.82	3.78
(ArC ₁ +ArC ₂)/ArC ₃ ^c	5.6	4.0	4.5	4.1

^a Guaiacyl and syringyl derived compounds; ^b Short and propanoid side chains; ^c Ratio between phenols with 1 and 2 carbons and 3 carbons in the side chains

Table 4. Phenolic content and efficient concentration (IC₅₀) of kraft lignin samples.

Samples	TPC	DPPH
	($\mu\text{g GAE/mg dry lignin}$)	IC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
KL	497.0 \pm 20.9	8.69
KLA	422.9 \pm 11.8	7.30
KLL	393.1 \pm 7.33	8.52
KLC	381.1 \pm 4.16	8.90
BHT	---	13.29
Ascorbic acid	---	2.90
Trolox	---	3.40

Table 5. Thermogravimetric parameters of different kraft lignin samples.

Samples	T_{1max} (°C)	wt%	T_{2max} (°C)	wt%	Char Yield at 800 °C (%)
KL	240.2	9.29	365.2	30.6	39.3
KLA	243.6	8.1	368.0	28.6	39.8
KLL	236.9	9.93	345.6	29.5	39.2
KLC	230.7	10.34	327.2	27.2	40.9

Table 6. Proximate analysis (% dry basis).

Samples	Moisture content %	Ash %	Volatile matter %	Fixed Carbon %	Organic matter %	HHV[32] (MJ/Kg)	HHV[33] (MJ/Kg)
KL	6.54	4.68	54.15	34.63	95.32	20.97	21.52
KLA	3.02	0.07	57.21	39.70	99.98	22.82	23.84
KLL	4.24	1.02	56.55	38.18	98.98	22.17	23.19
KLC	5.24	1.99	53.92	38.86	98.01	22.12	22.98